

at 14% moisture content was 86-92%.

The seeds were stored in paper bags, with the top folded twice and clipped, on wooden shelves Nov 1984-May 1987. Average and maximum and minimum room temperatures and relative humidity during storage are given in Table 1. A 300-seed sample was randomly drawn for each variety in May 1987; one-half of each sample was dehulled. The seeds were put in petri dishes on moist filter paper at room temperature for germination, with 50 seeds constituting a replication.

In general, germination percentage dropped over 30 mo storage. However, there was not much variation in germination between hulled and dehulled seeds. The varieties could be grouped into 3 classes on the basis of germination percentage: no germination, less than 25% germination, and more than 25% germination (Table 2).

Germination ranged from 0 (Salumpikit, Dourado Precoce) to 40% (IR10004-1-1-2), suggesting genetical control for this trait.

These genotypic differences could be used to save the effort of growing out

Table 2. Germination of 24 rice varieties before and after storage. Hazaribag, India.

Variety	Initial germination (%)	Germination (%) after 30 mo	
		Hulled grain	Dehulled grain
IR12919-24-1-8	88	39	38
IR10004-1-1-2	90	40	35
IR27095-20-3	92	35	37
IR6023-10-1-1	92	18	20
IR10120-7-2-1-4	92	22	16
Kinandang Patong	86	20	16
IAC47	89	12	10
IR54	92	8	7
IRAT13	87	7	6
IR38	90	6	6
AC540	90	6	6
H105	87	4	4
IRAT110	88	3	2
CR125-12-8	92	0	0
IAC25	92	0	0
IR34	92	0	0
IRAT109	92	0	0
Kulu	91	0	0
Ngoba	90	0	0
IRAT116	90	0	0
IRAT10	88	0	0
IAC165	88	0	0
Salumpikit	86	0	0
Dourado Precoce	86	0	0

entire germplasm collections every year. Varieties showing more than 25% germination could be stored for 2 yr and regenerated the third year. Genotypes

like IR12979-24-1-8, IR27095-20-3, and IR10004-1-1-2 could be used as donors for long storage life. □

Genetics

Isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus observed at rice vegetative and reproductive phases

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We analyzed IR36 and IR64 (indicas) and Taichung 65 (japonica) for isozyme polymorphism at vegetative and reproductive phases using three isozyme loci (*Est-2*, *Amp-3*, and *Pgi-2*). The analysis was to determine the allelic constitution for various isozyme loci used to study linkage relationships with the wide compatibility gene (*Sⁿ*). Isozyme polymorphism in the three cultivars is presented in the table.

Taichung 65 showed differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles at the vegetative

(*Est-2⁰*) and reproductive phases (*Est-2²*). Recently, differential behavior of *Est-2* alleles was reported in cold-tolerant rices. Cultivars possessing *Est-2⁰* allele were more tolerant than those with *Est-2¹* and *Est-2²*. Taichung 65 is known to show cold tolerance at the vegetative phase, but susceptibility at the reproductive phase.

This raises the question whether the isozyme polymorphism for *Est-2* locus

Isozyme polymorphism for 3 isozyme loci -- *Amp-3*, *Est-2*, and *Pgi-2* -- at vegetative and reproductive phases.^a IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Isozyme pattern					
	<i>Amp-3</i>		<i>Est-2</i>		<i>Pgi-2</i>	
	V	R	V	R	V	R
IR36	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
IR64	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²	2 ²
Taichung 65	3 ¹	3 ¹	2 ⁰	2 ²	2 ¹	2 ¹

^aV = at vegetative phase, R = at reproductive phase.

observed at vegetative and reproductive phases in Taichung 65 and other rice cultivars can be related to their cold tolerance at the two growth stages. □

Inheritance of high density grain in rice

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The parents, F₁, and F₂ of a cross of diverse parents IR30 and IR32385-37-3-3-3 (high density grain index [HDI] 56% and 29%, respectively) were grown in the greenhouse during 1987 wet season to study inheritance of this trait.

HDI was calculated by dividing the number of high density grains (specific gravity >1.20) by spikelets per panicle on primary (Pb) and secondary (Sb) branches (50 panicles of each parent and

the F_1 , 275 panicles of the F_2).

The F_1 population, with a wide range of variation (mean 76% Pb, 75% Sb), markedly exceeded the high parent (56%). The F_2 population had a continuous distribution—10-90% Pb and 20- to 90% Sb, mean of 60% Pb and 59% Sb. The curve was unimodal, but skewed somewhat negatively (see figure). Only a few plants exceeded the lower parental limit and 20% exceeded the upper limit of IR30, indicating that multiple genes with opposite effects were operating.

The dominance effect (Pb - 34.0, Sb - 34.2) was 2-3 times higher than the additive effects (Pb - 16.4, Sb - 12.0). The potence ratio was more than 2 (Pb - 2.16, Sb - 2.60), indicating over-dominance of genes governing this trait. The effective factor pairs estimate was

Distribution and means of parents, F_1 , and F_2 plants of IR30/IR32385-37-3-3-3 cross, by high density grain index. IRRI, 1987 wet season.

0.58 for Pb and 1.26 for Sb, indicating that the trait is controlled by a few genes of the polymeric model. The degree of heterosis was 86.76 (Pb), 69.96 (Sb); heterobeltiosis was 33.22 (Pb) and 33.92 (Sb).

The heritability estimate was very high, more than 80%. Thus, selections for more high density grain may be effective in early segregating generations such as F_3 or F_4 . We have selected 40 F_3 lines to evaluate in the F_4 . □

Yield potential

Performance of new Bw rice varieties compared to Bg 400-1 in Sri Lanka

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Bg 400-1 (Ob 678//IR20/H4), bred at Central Rice Breeding Centre, Batalagoda, Sri Lanka, is a very popular 4- to 4 1/2-mo variety because it adapts to diverse environments. Under good management, it has produced 7 t/ha in the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka.

However, panicle sterility, particularly in the yala season (Apr-Aug), has drastically reduced yields. To find a replacement for Bg 400-1, we evaluated lines in yala 1986 (Apr-Aug) and maha 1986/87 (Sep-Mar) in farmers' fields.

Bw 295-5 (Ob 678/Bw 254-1) and sister lines Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 (Bw 259-4/Bw 100) were chosen for field testing and comparison with Bg 400-1.

Trial sites represented the varying production potentials of diverse soil conditions in the low country wet zone.

Rice was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha in plots 6 × 4.5 m, with 30 cm space between plots.

Fertilizer and agrochemicals were applied as recommended in farmer-managed trials guided by field staff. Plot yields were converted to t/ha at 14% moisture level.

Average yields of the four varieties did not differ significantly. However, yields varied greatly within and across environments (13 locations in yala and 18 in maha), partly because of differing

soil fertility and farmer management levels.

Regression analysis showed that Bw 295-5 is as well adapted to a range of environments as is Bg 400-1. Bw 295-5 is similar to Bg 400-1 in plant height, tiller number, panicle length, grain color, and grain size.

Results show Bw 295-5 should be favorably considered. It is better than Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 in areas where Bg 400-1 is currently grown. □

Breeding methods

Substituting urea and boric acid for gibberellic acid in hybrid rice seed production

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The growth regulator gibberellic acid (GA_3) is used in hybrid rice seed production in China to increase panicle exertion, stigma exertion, and plant height and to synchronize flowering between primary and secondary tillers.

That helps increase outcrossing on the male sterile line and hybrid seed yield. But GA_3 is expensive (\$8/20 g) in countries outside China. When applied at 30-45 g/ha, costs soar. GA_3 also increases plant height, which induces lodging. The extra exerted panicles can break during the wet season (WS) under torrential rains and strong winds.

We looked for a suitable substitute for GA_3 . Hybrid seed production experiments with sorghum and pearl millet have shown the effectiveness of urea and boric acid sprays in increasing hybrid seed yields. These chemicals are available and cheap throughout the